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PRELIMINARY DATA CLASSIFICATION BY MULTILEVEL SEGMENTATION OF HISTOGRAMS FOR CLUSTERING OF HYPERCUBES

The object of research is an algorithm for the classification of large data based on the hierarchical clustering algorithm. The nonlinear complexity of the clustering algorithm does not allow for data samples of 5–10 thousand and above. To classify data, it is necessary to pre-group them. Therefore, the subject of research is the data segmentation algorithm based on piecewise linear approximation.

In the course of the study, let's use hierarchical clustering algorithms, the method of piecewise linear approximation of the cumulative histogram, calculated by a special procedure, and the procedure for searching for segmentation thresholds.

The computational complexity of the classical hierarchical algorithm reaches the value of $O(N^3)$, and certain steps to limit the search can achieve the value of $O(N^2)$, which is confirmed by experiments to study the dependence of the hierarchical tree on the initial sample. An approximate approach to key clustering with partitioning of a set of basic keys is implemented. To reduce further the complexity of the hierarchical clustering algorithm, a decomposition approach based on splitting the initial sample of large data into a number of subsets is proposed. In this article to use the hierarchical clustering algorithm for big data classification the preliminary decomposition method is proposed. It is based on multilevel segmentation of cumulative or ordinary histograms obtained for every feature coordinate characterizing object of data. Thresholds of multilevel segmentation are obtained by piecewise linear approximation of histogram functions. Build hypercubes of data are being accepted as objects for three stages clustering algorithm.

Powerful tool for data classification is obtained, the use of which allows carrying out many experiments with data of various types to identify patterns among the data features. Its application is intended for the processing of patient data, molecular structures, economic problems for making optimal treatment decisions, diagnostics and modeling. Thanks to this approach, data classification can be performed online to obtain the results of direct analysis when data is received, for example, from spacecraft.

Keywords: cumulative histogram, multilevel segmentation, piecewise linear approximation, hierarchical clustering, decomposition of data space.

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1. Introduction

Cluster analysis methods are widely used for decomposition, research, indexing and search, image recognition. In particular, work [1–3] contains a classification of clustering methods and a method for forming the contours of the selected clusters. Works [4–6] devoted to the clustering of graphs of models, which reflect parts of images. In papers [7–9] recent trends in practical algorithms for balanced graph partitioning point to applications and discuss future research directions are surveyed. The hierarchical clustering algorithm in [10] has one stage of the folding procedure and proposes a new criterion for combining to reduce computational costs from $O(N^3)$ complexity to $O(N^2)$.

For large amounts of data with many characteristics, this complexity is also an obstacle to grouping. Therefore, the work proposes several approaches to reduce complexity based on the decomposition of the cluster search space. The first attempts of the authors were demonstrated in

works [11–13]. In the study [14] an empirical analysis involving a multi-variable quantitative analysis was used to examine the factors that influence the performance of the innovation cluster.

Presented investigations are actual because nowadays there are a big amount of patients with symptoms of coronavirus whose tests need to be processed as well as characteristics of the disease to find patterns, reasons and medicaments. In practice a number of patients is millions and clustering of hypercubes is a good instrument for these purposes.

The object of research is an algorithm for the classification of large data based on the hierarchical clustering algorithm. The classification algorithm having two stages: preliminary segmentation of the object space to form their groups with similar characteristics and clustering of hypercubes having common coordinates and without them. The aim of research is to reduce radically a complexity of the clustering algorithm which are planned to be applied for big data.

2. Methods of research

Clustering is one of the instruments to analyze data to know its structure and perform their classification. To build clusters of objects, an algorithm for grouping them by similar characteristics must be realized. An illustration of image pixel clusters having the same colors is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Examples of clustered images: *a* – for 5 clusters; *b* – for 9 clusters

One of wide spread methods is the agglomerative hierarchical clustering algorithm. It includes the following steps:

- S0. For all elements of the input set $x_i, x_j \in X$.
- S1. Searching of leaf pairs by the similarity function:

$$\forall(x_i, x_j) \text{ calculate } F(x_i, x_j). \quad (1)$$

- S2. Comparison and selection of pairs with the smallest distance value:

$$F^*(x_i, x_j) = \min F(x_i, x_j), \quad i, j \in I. \quad (2)$$

For merging the clusters x_i, x_j in a new cluster x_n .

- S3. Recalculate the cluster's centers x_i^0 ($i=1, \dots, k$).
- S4. Remove clusters x_i, x_j from the list of candidates.
- S5. End of the procedure (for all $x_i, x_j \in X$).

In this algorithm for the measure of approximation between two clusters is used the distance between their centers of gravity or their centers of coordinates:

$$F(A, B) = d(i_c, j_c), \quad (3)$$

where a hypothetical object i_c is a centroid of the cluster A , and j_c is a centroid of the cluster B .

The centroid has as many features as every object in the input set or a cluster. So, the function F is being accepted as a weighted sum of modules of differences between the characteristics of centroids:

$$F_{ij} = w_1 |a_i - a_j| + w_2 |b_i - b_j| + w_3 |c_i - c_j| + \dots, \quad (4)$$

or weighted sum of squares of the differences between the characteristics of centroids:

$$F_{ij} = w_1 [a_i - a_j]^2 + w_2 [b_i - b_j]^2 + w_3 [c_i - c_j]^2 + \dots \quad (5)$$

When two clusters are being merged coordinated of new centroid are recalculated by the following:

$$C_k = C_k \left(\frac{k^* a_i + r^* a_j}{k+r}, \frac{k^* b_i + r^* b_j}{k+r}, \dots \right). \quad (6)$$

The algorithm builds a binary hierarchical convolution tree (dendrogram) of the object clusters by the proximity function. An example of the tree for a clustering process as a dendrogram is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Dendrogram of clustering process

In this dendrogram the vertical axis shows the value between the nodes merged together to create a new node. Each node in the graph besides leaves marks a cluster with a corresponding number of elementary objects.

Algorithmic complexity $O(N^2)$ of the classic hierarchical algorithm does not allow to classify a large data sample, for example, images of practical sizes. For these purposes some approaches based on decomposition technique could be considered.

3. Research results and discussion

3.1. Space decomposition to hypercubes. To reduce the algorithmic complexity the initial set of objects $H(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, \dots, Q_N)$ is being divided into p subsets $H_1(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, \dots, Q_z)$, $H_2(Q_{z+1}, Q_{z+2}, Q_{z+3}, \dots, Q_t)$, ..., $H(Q_{t+1}, Q_{t+2}, Q_{t+3}, \dots, Q_N)$.

In common, the main input data hypercube must be divided into a number of smaller hypercubes. For the 3-dimension case in Fig. 3 $m \times k \times n$ hypercubes are shown, obtained by dividing corresponding coordinate intervals into m, k, n parts.

Fig. 3. Decomposition of data space into smaller hypercubes

As examples, consider two possible types of decomposition: hypercubes of different sizes, but with the same numbers of data objects and small hypercubes having the same size and different numbers of objects. These cases are illustrated by division of coordinate intervals for 2-dimension space in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Decomposition of 2-dimension space: *a* – objects in original 2-cube; *b* – equal numbers of objects; *c* – equal sizes of 2-cubes sides

Fig. 13. Examples of hierarchical trees: *a* – for hypercubes in Fig. 9 and in Fig. 10; *b* – for hypercubes in Fig. 12

Fig. 14. Images of objects (white pixels): *a* – two rectangles are isolated; *b* – two rectangles are overlapped

This example changes the cumulative histogram (not of the image but of numbers of white pixels in columns and rows) by ordinary histogram (also by numbers) and the last one by a pixel intensity function in the W columns and H rows of the image matrix:

$$\bar{I}(i) = \frac{1}{W} \sum_{j=1}^W I(i, j), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, H,$$

$$\bar{I}(j) = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{i=1}^H I(i, j), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, W, \quad (13)$$

where $I(i, j)$ is pixel intensity in i -row and j -column ($1 \leq i \leq H, 1 \leq j \leq W$).

To do such an exchange it is possible only if objects are as white pixels and background is black. The goal of this exchange is to demonstrate robustness of the algorithm to different models of data presentation: cumulative histograms, histograms and mean intensity functions.

Mean intensity functions for rectangles are calculated. To determine coordinates of vertical and horizontal bands to build the grid, these functions are approximated by piecewise linear functions, which are given in Fig. 15.

So axis OX will be divided in five intervals by point of 87, 233, 269, 495. The axis OY will be divided also in five intervals by point of 61, 164, 196, 287.

By coordinate values of the function intervals the space for hypercubes (9 cells) is being built in Fig. 16 (in our case the grid with uneven steps). Objects are imaginary placed in corresponding hypercubes (here cells). Fully independent parts of input data are marked with different

colors, belonging to the white rectangles and those having common coordinates with other rectangle. Steps of the grid reflect them by axes OX and OY .

Fig. 15. Mean intensity functions for images of rectangles: *a* – in rows; *b* – in columns

Fig. 16. Images of objects placed on the classification grid: *a* – for isolated rectangles; *b* – for overlapped rectangles

Consider one more experiment with data being of more complicated structure (Fig. 17, *a*). Missing the intermediates calculations given in previous examples, the grid of obtained hypercubes is presented (Fig. 17, *b*). The independent hypercubes are marked by lighter colors and hypercubes having common features are marked by darker colors.

Fig. 17. Figures of pixels for clustering: *a* – initial image of white pixels; *b* – hypercubes of pixels on the classification grid

From resulting images of experiments it is clear that further clustering algorithm is needed to perform clustering to the root. But now in Fig. 16 the space of the input data is much less than at the beginning. For the case of Fig. 16, *a*, there are 4 objects, for the second image in Fig. 16, *b* there are 7 objects. For the grid in Fig. 17, *b* there are 18 objects.

The hierarchical tree is being built for objects representing hypercubes in Fig. 16, *a*, and it is shown in Fig. 18.

Fig. 18. Hierarchical tree of hypercubes

Two examples of 3-D objects and distribution them in hypercubes are illustrated by simple images. For rectangles in Fig. 19, *a* having 5 colors and 5 intervals in every coordinate there are $5 \times 5 \times 5 = 125$ hypercubes and for rectangles in Fig. 19, *b* having 10 colors and 2 intervals in every coordinate there are $10 \times 2 \times 2 = 40$ hypercubes. These hypercubes are taken as leaves for clustering by below considered algorithms.

Fig. 19. Pixels of image as 3-D objects: *a* – grouping in 125 hypercubes; *b* – grouping in 40 hypercubes

The decomposition process for not discrete example given in Fig. 20 is now illustrated.

For white pixels as objects to be classified, four histograms of white pixels in rows and columns: ordinary and cumulative (Fig. 21) are calculated. It can be seen that ordinary histograms have oscillations connected with distribution of objects in the space. Cumulative histograms have no such peculiarities which influence on the result of approximation.

Fig. 20. White pixel as objects: *a* – in original image; *b* – divided by multilevel segmentation of histogram

Fig. 21. Ordinary and cumulative histograms of white pixels: *a* – in rows; *b* – in columns

To get coordinates of multilevel segmentation these functions were approximated (Fig. 22). The difference between two approximation functions can be seen. For ordinary histogram approximation function has 13 intervals the end points of them could be taken as coordinates of hypercube. For cumulative histogram approximation function there are four intervals to build a hypercube.

Fig. 22. Approximated by the RDP algorithm ordinary and cumulative histogram functions in rows

According to coordinates of approximated functions a space of the image is being divided into rectangles (for 3-D into cubes and hypercubes). Approximation of cumulative histograms for pixels in row and columns gives $5 \times 6 = 30$ rectangles in Fig. 20, b which are being accepted as input data for the next algorithms.

3.4. Three stages clustering algorithm of hypercubes.

After decomposition of the data space into a number of hypercubes of objects to data classification continues by a consequence of clustering algorithms. They are applied to data objects in hypercubes and to objects obtained from hypercubes by clustering.

3.4.1. Algorithm of clustering in cascades.

– S0. Leaves for clustering are being prepared: for two cascades they are copied from hypercubes, for many cascades they are copied from a list of resulting clusters (S3).

– S1. Objects of every hypercube $H(H_1, H_2, \dots, H_p)$ are clustered by hierarchical agglomerative algorithm. Sets of the clusters $K_1(k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots), K_2(k_s, k_{s+1}, k_{s+2}, \dots), \dots, K_p(k_r, k_{r+1}, k_{r+2}, \dots)$ are obtained and k_1, k_2, \dots, k_i are clusters of objects from hypercubes H_1, H_2, \dots, H_p . A number of resulting clusters depends on the coefficient k_r (1, 0.95, ..., 0.01) indicating a reduction ratio of the object's number in a hypercube. So, a resulting number can be from one to full number of objects in the hypercube. The reduction coefficient control time consumption and accuracy of the algorithm.

– S2. Resulting clusters are being accepted as input objects for a new set of leaves:

$$K = K_1(k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots) \cup \cup K_2(k_s, k_{s+1}, k_{s+2}, \dots) \cup \dots \cup K_p(k_r, k_{r+1}, k_{r+2}, \dots). \quad (14)$$

– S3. Control for next steps is transferred to steps S0 and S1 to continue merging and to build the binary hierarchical tree.

The procedure of so-called multilevel cascading clustering is illustrated by Fig. 23.

Fig. 23. Decomposition of leaves and clustering trees

Decomposition of basic leaves (data objects) could be arbitrary (random) or controlled by some rules.

Hypercubes obtained from segmentation technique are between themselves in the following relations: some of them are neighbors and have common borders as lines, planes etc., other hypercubes are touching between themselves by one point, and the last group of hypercubes has no relations, i. e. they are isolated by empty space. In such consequence works the proposed clustering algorithm.

The hierarchical clustering algorithm (1)–(6) is applied to hypercubes obtained by decomposition technique. Hypercubes are not trivial objects with a set of features. That is why a clustering procedure is being modified. Every hypercube is characterized by a set of features some of which are also sets: N_i is a number of objects; $x_i(x_{i_1}, x_{i_2}, x_{i_3}, x_{i_4})$ are coordinates of a center; $b_i(b_{i_1}, b_{i_2}, b_{i_3}, b_{i_4})$ are borders of a hypercube; s_i is a square. Hypercubes have two types of borders: internal ones connecting the current hypercube with a neighbor and external ones being borders to free space (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24. Two types of hypercube borders

3.4.2. Algorithm for clustering of hypercubes. The algorithm for clustering of hypercubes consists of a consequence of main steps:

– S0. Formation of a control list P of pointers to adjoining hypercubes.

– S1. Selection the two best candidates for merging. There are some strategies of clustering in this step:

a) to select minimal distance between centroids of hypercubes:

$$F^* = \min(F_{ij}), \quad k, j \in P, \quad (15)$$

where F presents distance between centroids:

$$F = d_{ij}(\omega_1 |a_i - a_j| + \omega_2 |b_i - b_j| + \omega_3 |c_i - c_j| + \dots); \quad (16)$$

b) to select maximal number of objects in the resulting cluster:

$$F^* = \max(F_{kj}), \quad k, j \in P, \quad (17)$$

where

$$F_{kj} = n_k + n_j; \quad (18)$$

c) to minimize displacements of a center of gravity of a new hypercube comparatively to every participant of merging:

$$F^* = \min(F_{ij}), \quad i, j \in P, \quad (19)$$

where

$$F_{ij} = \frac{\min\{|C_i - C_n|, |C_j - C_n|\}}{d_{ij}}, \quad (20)$$

where C_i, C_j are centers of gravity of candidates to be merged; C_n is a center of the new cluster:

$$C_n = C_n \left(\frac{k^*a_i + r^*a_j}{k+r}, \frac{k^*b_i + r^*b_j}{k+r}, \dots \right). \quad (21)$$

– S2. To build a new hypercubes from both selected, deleting of data connected with merged hypercubes and determination of features for new hypercube.

Three criteria for searching of candidates are used to control a type of the built clusters. First criterion is traditional to consider only distances and minimize it. Second criterion is planned to form maximal clusters on low level of the tree. Third criterion is planned to join small parts to greater ones at the beginning of clustering process.

Very important characteristic of the algorithm is a so called control panel of the convolution process. The panel contains pointers connected with internal borders of hypercubes. So, they point on hypercubes which are candidates to be merged (Fig. 25). Merging process is being continued until the list of the pointers will become empty.

Fig. 25. Pointers on hypercubes

At this point the first stage of the clustering algorithm is being terminated. The second stage begins to work with a control list filled by new pointers. They correspond to the angle points common to two hypercubes (Fig. 26, a). The second stage could be excluded if isolated hypercubes in result are preferable.

Fig. 26. Two types of hypercubes: *a* – having one common point; *b* – without common elements

And the last stage of the algorithm works then two control panels will be empty and objects for clustering are isolated that is all obtained clusters will be as closed areas (Fig. 26, b).

Fig. 27 shows the clustering tree for hypercubes in Fig. 28. It gives distinct two clusters shown by the dendrogram. Gray lines correspond to the first stage of the algorithm, blue lines correspond to the hypercubes having one common point and red lines correspond to the third stage of the algorithm. Ordinary algorithm does not allow to get such a result because distances within the same cluster could be greater than distances between different clusters.

Fig. 27. Hierarchical trees of hypercubes

Fig. 28. Example of hypercubes on the classification grid

Above described experiments show that reducing the input data for the clustering algorithm (a number of hypercubes are radically smaller than a number of input objects) a complexity of the classification algorithm is being reduced drastically. The proposed type of segmentation of data space by every coordinate allows to classify objects placed in spaces of complicated architecture.

4. Conclusions

The algorithm of data preliminary classification by decomposition of its space into hypercubes is developed. Coordinates of hypercubes are obtained when the ordinary and cumulative histogram functions are approximated by piecewise linear functions. Then hypercubes are clustered by three stages clustering algorithm: hypercubes having common borders, having common point and isolated areas. Algorithm allows to classify data having complex structure and large size.

A novelty of the proposed classification algorithm lies in a type of data segmentation based on linear piecewise approximation of the cumulative histogram. The cumulative histogram is calculated for objects as white pixels

for every coordinate. Data hypercubes are considered of two types: adjacent and independent. This proposed and realized novelty reduces the algorithm complexity allowing its application to very big data.

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